

Changes and Challenges in Grid Environment

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Abstract —Grid computing has recently migrated from traditional high performance and distributed computing to pervasive and utility computing based on the advanced capabilities of the wireless networks and the lightweight, thin devices. This has resulted the emergence of a new computing paradigm “Mobile Grid”. This paper provides a discussion on Mobile Grid definition, the basic motivation and benefits that can stem from this new technology, especially as far as it concerns collaborative engineering, industry and in everyday life of the “mobile” citizen. In the sequel it presents a set of major technical topics that influence the traditionally basic Grid Infrastructure services under the new Grid environment involving Mobile Grids.

Keywords — Virtual organization, Cluster Grid, Heap Sort Tree, Grid Resource Description Language (GRDL).

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical things for understanding and realizing Mobile Grid computing is to have a consistent and accurate definition, or at least determination of what a Mobile Grid is. There are many attempts for the accurate definition of the Grid. However the various approaches that have been made address in a high degree of accuracy the term Grid. The Grid can be viewed as a distributed, high performance computing and data handling infrastructure, that incorporates geographically and organizationally dispersed, heterogeneous resources (computing systems, storage systems, instruments and other real-time data sources, human collaborators, communication systems) and provides common interfaces for all these resources, using standard, open, general-purpose protocols and interfaces [1]. However, it is also the basis and the enabling technology for pervasive and utility computing due to the ability of being open, highly heterogeneous and scalable. Mobile Computing is a generic term describing the application of small, portable, and wireless computing and communication devices. This includes devices like Laptops with Wireless Local Area Networks technology, mobile phones, and Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs) with Bluetooth or Infrared Data Association (IrDA) interfaces. The Mobile Computing focuses on the requirement of providing access to information, communications and services everywhere, anytime and by any available means. The technical solutions for achieving this are not always easy to implement. In fact, mobile computing requires the creation of communication infrastructures and the modification of computer networks, operating systems, and application programs. The mobility issue implies some constraints that must be addressed since they limit the capability of a moving resource in contrast to a fixed one. Mobile Grid, in relevance to both Grid and Mobile Computing, is a full inheritor of Grid with the additional feature of supporting mobile users

and resources in a seamless, transparent, secure and efficient way. It has the ability to deploy underlying ad-hoc networks and provide a self-configuring Grid system of mobile resources (hosts and users) connected by wireless links and forming arbitrary and unpredictable topologies.

WHAT IS GRID?

Grids have moved from the obscurely academic to the highly popular. The skeptic can be forgiven for wondering if there is more to the Grid than, as one wag put it, a “funding concept”—and, as industry becomes involved, a marketing slogan. If by deploying a scheduler on my local area network I create a “Cluster Grid,” then doesn’t my Network File System deployment over that same network provides me with a “Storage Grid?” Indeed, isn’t my workstation, coupling as it does processor, memory, disk, and network card, a “PC Grid?” Is there any computer system that isn’t a Grid? Ultimately the Grid must be evaluated in terms of the applications, business value, and scientific results that it delivers, not its architecture[1]. Nevertheless, the questions above must be answered if Grid computing is to obtain the credibility and focus that it needs to grow and prosper. In this and other respects, our situation is similar to that of the Internet in the early 1990s. Back then, vendors were claiming that private networks such as SNA and DECNET were part of the Internet, and others were claiming that every local area network was a form of Internet. This confused situation was only clarified when the Internet Protocol (IP) became widely adopted for both wide area and local area networks.

THE EVOLUTION OF GRID COMPUTING

The main objective of any grid system type is found in sharing networked, potentially geographically dispersed resources, whose utilities are made available by means of standardized interfaces. Traditional grid systems focused

mainly on sharing resources in order to solve computational or data-intensive tasks. To this aim, clusters consisting of relatively inexpensive networked computers and/or storage facilities were used. The grid nodes usually formed one administrative domain, run by a single, typically research oriented organization. Those first grid systems are called computational grids and data grids, depending on whether such a grid emphasizes more on computational or storage-related issues. The next evolutionary step in grid systems' development happened on the organizational model that became applicable due to the coordination of resources out of different administrative domains. While resource types remained the same, namely network infrastructure, computational power, and storage facility, this new grid system category introduced a service layer on top of the resource pool across administrative domains. Hence, the novelty of such service-oriented grid systems, called service grids, consists in forming a virtual organization (VO) [2]. In service grids, various resources are encapsulated by means of grid services — Web Services with well-defined interfaces and following certain conventions — that are in turn made available for authorized VO members. Service grids facilitate computational and data grids to adopt service-orientation concepts, so that these traditional grid systems also profit from grid service provisioning across administrative borders. Inter-domain service provisioning in service grids determines today the state-of-the-art in grid computing not only for community-driven grids, but also for many commercial solutions. However, most of the commercial grid solutions are nowadays targeted towards enterprise-wide implementation, so that they make use of the service-orientation aspect in service grids, whereas rather virtual teams than virtual organizations are built. Service grid concepts triggered again new challenges to be addressed by so-called next-generation grid systems. Those challenges mostly deal with increased complexity. Most importantly, but in terms of a non-comprehensive listing, this embraces the coordination of higher-level resources, such as knowledge, the support of dynamic virtual organizations (DVO), and the commercialization of grid services. All these aspects are of center stage for the mobile grid as it is designed and prototypically implemented in the EU project Akogrimo[10].

THE NEED FOR GRID TECHNOLOGIES

Grid technologies support the sharing and coordinated use of diverse resources in dynamic VOs—that is, the creation, from geographically and organizationally distributed components, of virtual computing systems that are sufficiently integrated to deliver desired QoS [2]. Grid concepts and technologies were first developed to enable resource sharing within far-flung scientific collaborations. Applications include collaborative visualization of large scientific datasets (pooling of expertise), distributed

computing for computationally demanding data analyses (pooling of compute power and storage), and coupling of scientific instruments with remote computers and archives (increasing functionality as well as availability).

We expect similar applications to become important in commercial settings, initially for scientific and technical computing applications (where we can already point to success stories) and then for commercial distributed computing applications, including enterprise application integration and business to business (B2B) partner collaboration over the Internet. Just as the World Wide Web began as a technology for scientific collaboration and was adopted for e-business, we expect a similar trajectory for Grid technologies. Nevertheless, we argue that Grid concepts are critically important for commercial computing not primarily as a means of enhancing capability, but rather as a solution to new challenges relating to the construction of reliable, scalable, and secure distributed systems. These challenges derive from the current rush, driven by technology trends and commercial pressures, to decompose and distribute through the network previously monolithic host-centric services, as we now discuss.

WHY MOBILE GRID?

Grid is already being successfully used in many scientific applications where huge amounts of data have to be processed and/or stored. Such demanding applications have created, justified and diffused the concept of Grid among the scientific community. As the amount of potential Grid users is really enormous, the accumulated data processing and storage requirements are at least comparable. Wireless devices (laptops and PDAs), with currently limited resources (low processing power, finite battery life and constrained storage space), would benefit from the opportunity of using a considerable amount of resources made available by all the other devices connected to the network [3]. In particular, mobile users might be the future users of this new technology. Moreover, we have nomadic users who travel and work only seldom at their offices. Mobile Grid enables both the mobility of the users requesting access to a fixed Grid and the resources that are themselves part of the Grid. Both cases have their own limitations and constraints that should be handled [5]. In the first case the devices of the mobile users act as interfaces to the Grid enabling job submission, monitoring and management of the activities in an 'anytime, anywhere' mode, while the Grid provides them with a high reliability, performance and cost-efficiency. Physical limitations of the mobile devices make necessary the adaptation of the services that Grid can provide to the users' mobile devices. In those cases mobile Grid has the meaning of 'gridifying' the mobile resources. In the second case of having mobile Grid resources, we should underline

that the performances of current mobile devices are significantly increased. Laptops and PDAs can provide aggregated computational capability when gathered in hotspots, forming a Grid on site. This capability can advantage the usage of Grid applications even in places where this would be imaginary. However, there will always be the question on why a Grid solution should be adopted in comparison to any other non-Grid Information Technology (IT) solution. Grid is not intended to be the ‘panacea’ to the problems related to IT domain. It is a promising emerging technology that has the ambition to provide more efficient and beneficial solution than its ‘competitors’ by enabling the simple ‘connect and share’ approach in the same manner as the current Internet search engines apply the ‘connect and acquire information’ concept. By this, Grids and mobile Grids can be the ideal solution for many large scale applications that are of dynamic nature and require transparency for users.

WHAT IS ‘MOBILE’ IN A MOBILE GRID?

Mobile Grid is a platform that should address mobility issues by means of enabling both fixed and mobile users to have access to both fixed and mobile Grid resources utilizing transparently and efficiently the underlying technologies. Mobility involves a set of issues for both users and communication/collaboration mode that will be presented shortly in the sequel. Nomadic users move around between different terminals and ask session movement (user mobility). For example, a user can open a session on a workstation at his office and then ask its movement to a personal computer at home. Roaming users, instead, moving around with their own wireless devices, want to continue their sessions when they cross different localities, as it happens today in cell phones telecommunications (terminal mobility). In both cases the middleware should hide the details of the dynamic utilization of service components, when the session movement is required, besides it should manage all the session hand-off transparently to the user and possibly to the application components. Another kind of mobility is the service mobility which is meant as the ability of the infrastructure to maintain the services for a user while he is mobile. These services should be independent from the devices and from the location of the user with respect to the network he is accessing [8]. Another aspect of mobility that should be considered is the distinction between wireless networking and mobile user interfaces. In wireless networking the problem relies in the fact that the connection is highly variable both in quality and in price, and moreover that disconnections happen unexpectedly, thus constituting synchronous interaction uncertain. In case of mobile user interfaces the challenges come from the restrictions imposed by the small device size. Small displays can only present limited amount of information, while absence of keyboard

makes data entry hard [5]. It should be noticed that mobility stresses the fact of the synchronous mode of communication. In a collaboration environment the most challenging aspect is to enable a synchronous mode of co-operation between the peer entities. While asynchronous mode is easier to be implemented in unreliable and complex environments, the synchronous mode introduces a set of constraints that are by nature difficult to handle.

WHAT’S NEW ABOUT MOBILE GRIDS?

Mobile grids offer a wide variety of possible applications. They can reach both geographic locations and social settings that computers have not traditionally penetrated. Wireless grids present three novel elements: new resources, new places of use, and new institutional ownership and control patterns. Wireless devices bring new resources to distributed computing [11]. In addition to typical computational resources such as processor power, disk space, and applications, wireless devices increasingly employ cameras, microphones, GPS receivers, and accelerometers, as well as an assortment of network interfaces (cell, radio, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth). One important class of devices is sensors, which can supply information on temperature, health, or pollution levels. People increasingly take wireless devices with them to new places, in both their personal and professional lives.

Figure 1. Dynamic and fixed wireless grids. Here we see two types of wireless grids: those composed of unknown mobile users and devices engaged in ad hoc resource sharing and service creation in a particular location, and those composed of components with known identities managed within a stable institutional structure.

The numbers of those devices that include sensors is growing. In fact, the pervasive mobile phone is developing into a super-sensor. From shopping malls to medical disaster areas, sporting events, and warehouse floors, wireless devices — and the sensors in them — are on the verge of becoming ubiquitous. Wireless grids present an opportunity to leverage available resources by enabling sharing between wireless and non-wireless resources.

CHALLENGES OF RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN MOBILE GRIDS

Grid computing has been a hot spot recent year. In grid computing applications, resource management and job scheduling are the most crucial problems in grid computing systems [6]. In this paper, we try to present a novel agent-based dynamic grid resource management model considering both the resource management and job scheduling as coalition integrity, so as to gain good robust, scalability, efficiency, and high performance. In this model, we use a carefully designed agent to obtain dynamic real time available computational ability of various nodes in the grid environment, so that new job could be assigned to the node that has the largest available computational power, and thus to improve system load ability and performance with good load balance.

We construct all grid computational resources into two-layered Heap Sort Tree (HST); this makes the system be more scalable, robust, fault-tolerant and high performance. By taking advantages of agents in constructing and reconstructing the two-layered HST, this model is well fitted with the unpredictable changing grid environment.

Resource Discovery and Selection

The volatile and dynamic environment of the mobile Grid makes necessary the use of sophisticated mechanisms for resource discovery and selection. The list of the authorized machines and resources that are available in the Grid infrastructure is continuously updated. The selection of those resources that are expected to meet the time or cost constraints imposed by the user has to be based not only on deterministic criteria but also on stochastic parameters, thus providing complex probabilistic models for the topology of the Grids and their capabilities. Some of the required parameters are resource accessibility, system workload, network performance, etc. Not to forget that the target audience of the mobile Grids is the broad spectrum of the citizens who would like to use the Grid for solving problems of their everyday life. Thus, a financial criterion of the resources used should be under consideration for the proper resource selection.

Resource Description

Resource description is a basic requirement for resource sharing. Before any group of devices can discuss needs and available resources, it must first agree on the manner in which to describe the resources. For example, if a group of devices wishes to share processor cycles, it must first be able to describe the processing requirements and capabilities. A variety of schemes provide for resource description; none of the schemes covers all resources, but taken together, they define most of the shared resources. Different resource-sharing systems undertake the task of resource description in

different ways. For example, P2P music-sharing networks utilize the filename and ID3 metadata tags. Resource Discovery Standards such as the IETF's ZeroConf, Microsoft's Universal Plug and Play, the Grid Resource Description Language (GRDL), standardized service-specific definitions using WSDL, and bandwidth descriptions from various QoS standards include resource-description protocols. Using these description vocabularies, devices can formulate their needs and publish their resources.

Coordination Systems

Coordination systems allow one device to utilize another device's resources, or permit the pooling and scheduling of resources. Each device can use a range of familiar mechanisms to share different resources. For example, to share disk space, a device might use NFS, Samba, or WebDav as the coordination mechanism. On the other hand, to share processor cycles, a device might use the distributed.net client as the coordination mechanism. The new resources that nomadic devices make available raise new challenges in coordination of resource sharing. For example, people are still developing the coordination systems devices for sharing and aggregating sensor data. Facilitating the sharing of screens and audio-visual inputs will require new coordination mechanisms. Right now, even having laptop users share a projector as an output device during a meeting calls for much fiddling with cables. We have argued elsewhere¹ that a new sharing protocol could serve as a metaprotocol to support resource description, discovery, coordination, and trust establishment, but have not yet begun to test and evaluate how such a protocol might perform in practice.

Trust Establishment

Clearly, a resource-sharing transaction requires trust. Indeed, each element in a transaction might even require a different type of trust establishment. For example, before you provide a description of your available resources, you might want to be certain of the identity of the device or user that you are talking with, perhaps via an institutionalized identity system such as a public-key infrastructure or Kerberos.

Clearing Mechanisms

A key component of a resource-sharing transaction is a clearing mechanism that establishes conditions under which a partner device or group of devices will extend access to the requesting device or group. This includes mechanisms that typically fall within an authorization process, but extend well beyond it. We use the term "clearing" in its economic sense, referring to the action (usually payment) required to "clear" or settle a market transaction. Most resource-sharing systems don't currently implement complex conditions for accessing resources. Typically, systems grant access to resources based

on the ability of a device, service, or user to prove membership to an appropriate class. Common clearing protocols are Kerberos and X.509, which the OGSA toolkit uses. Resource-sharing systems, such as P2P networks, that are outside the institutional environments in which schemes like Kerberos operate have innovated in this area and typically employ some form of quid-pro-quo exchange with their users. This sometimes means requiring users to run the full client — meaning that, in exchange for access to the network, they share the files they download. Other systems, such as BitTorrent, reserve superior service for network nodes that also provide uploads. We also anticipate resource-sharing situations in which bartering available resources for the period of their use will make economic sense, as in an effective power trading network. The range of clearing mechanisms can clearly extend to complex market situations.

JOB SCHEDULING

The Job Scheduling problem is classified as an NP-complete problem [6] [7] due to the fact that an algorithm has to be applied that would allocate jobs to resources in an efficient and cost effective manner, so as to minimize the resource utilization gaining the maximum profit and satisfying at the same time the user constraints (Security, Quality of Service, Fault tolerance etc). In a mobile Grid environment there are many more constraints that would make the job scheduling problem more complicated [6]. The cost of resources is in that case a metric that is subject to context parameters. Imagine what can happen in a big conference room where the aggregated performance due to the many notebooks linked in wireless hotspots can result in a very cost effective solution for “instant” high performance computing [5]. So the optimization criteria for a job scheduling mechanism should take under consideration not only the cost and the performance of each resource, but also the current availability of resources in the context and their reliability in providing the specific resources for the execution of the job under the given QoS constraints.

JOB REPLICATION, MIGRATION AND MONITORING

In accordance to the previous Job Scheduling issue, we claim that the mobile grid is a dynamic system where environmental conditions are subject to unpredictable changes: system or network failures, system performance degradation, addition of new machines, variations in the cost of resources, etc. In such context job migration and re-scheduling, as well as job replication and co-scheduling are both (from different perspectives) efficient ways to guarantee the completion of the jobs according to the restrictions set by the users. Job monitoring and checkpointing (especially in the case of long running tasks) is difficult in dynamic environments. Especially job monitoring is responsible for detecting alert situations that could initiate a migration and

alternatively identify if a job has been completed so as to suspend/stop/cancel the execution of the other replicas.

REPLICA MANAGEMENT FOR LARGE DATA SETS

Replica management is an important issue for a number of applications that utilize large data sets (like for instance experimental results for scientific applications, for simulations and prediction models) [7]. The complete data set of a VO may exist in one or possibly several physical locations but it is possible that no single organization has sufficient storage to hold a complete copy. Instead, the common practice is to have copies of the most relevant portions of the data set stored on local storage for faster access. Replica Management keeps track of where portions of the data set can be found by providing mappings between logical names for files and one or more copies of the files on physical storage systems.

This mapping is of particular interest in mobile environments, since access to specific physical locations might be impossible. Storage devices are constantly changing their connection status and sometimes their physical location, thus imposing different schemes for accessing their data, which includes context aware information. Moreover, mobile Grids have to address the issue of not only locating a Data Base containing the relative data, but also if this location is the most suitable and reliable (with respect to avoiding a failure) to be used.

WHAT WILL CHANGE AND AFFECT?

The mobile Grid will introduce changes to the general Grid concept. New functionalities of the Grid will be needed since the old ones will not make use of all the capabilities that will be available. These functionalities will involve end-to-end solutions with emphasis on Quality of Service (QoS) and security, as well as interoperability issues between the diverse technologies involved. Enhanced security policies and approaches to address large scale and heterogeneous environments will be needed. Additionally, the volatile, mobile and poor networked environments have to be addressed with adaptable QoS aspects which have to be contextualized with respect to users and their profiles. Mobile Grids will make use of the value that many mobile users perceive due to the advanced capabilities of their mobile devices. These advanced capabilities refer to the comparison of today’s mobile devices with the ones that existed in the past. Although mobile devices are subject to physical constraints due to their nature they have the ability of having computational and storage capabilities similar to PCs, high quality displays, multiple interfaces (for instance Bluetooth, Ethernet adapters, USB, Infrared) etc. This value can be converted into revenue for service providers. This implies changes in various business models and policy issues. Complex workflows for businesses will be needed and

Virtual Organizations (VO) [2] will be enriched with the opportunity for automatic federations and resource sharing schemes. Valuations of the diverse services and especially with respect to the Service/Sharing level agreement have to be adapted in relation to QoS aspects. Enterprises have to issue policies that will handle the conflict between public rights to their users and viable models for operation. Moreover the fair use of Grid must be determined by reconciling rights of public access to resources and private ownership of infrastructure and resources.

EXISTING WORK

There are some efforts focusing on designing and developing the Mobile Grid. However they are in a preliminary form and are expected to provide the first results by end of 2005. The K*Grid project [9] is an initiative in Grid research supported by Korean Ministry of Information and Communication. The main goal of the K*Grid project is to provide a powerful research environment to both industries and academia. In this project, a study on mobile grid technologies is elaborated that uses idle resources of a great number of mobile devices and the development of a mobile grid platform[9]. The scope of the effort includes the analysis of wireless mobile networks, devices and technologies and the requirements for mobile grid, design and implementation of mobile grid platform which is based on PDA and wireless LAN technology.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented the Grid Technology concept, the recent changes in the Grid Technology, Mobile Grid and the challenges that have to be met in order to address the new computing paradigm, mainly focused on the aspect of resource management, which is the heart of every Grid functionality. Paper indicates the necessity for research in this domain so as to enable the implementation of the new Mobile Grid environment. Moreover, the paper presented the existing work and projects worldwide which are promising for the elaboration of the domain. As the Grid computing seems to gain more space in the technology area, it will be the basis for utility and pervasive computing in the forthcoming years by leveraging the mobility advantage that will be enhanced with Mobile Grid. The future work in this area will investigate not only the issues concerning the interoperability but also the efficiency of mobile Grid solutions so as to enable the deployment of Mobile Grids in commercial and everyday life applications.

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